

Event-based shape learning through visual attention

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Abstract Despite significant advancements in modern artificial intelligence, human visual object recognition remains markedly superior in terms of generalizability and adaptability. For example, when encountering a novel object, humans can readily distinguish it from dissimilar ones, a task that remains challenging for modern AI systems. Active vision leverages visual exploration over time to associate visual characteristics and link them to sensorimotor contingencies, enabling object discrimination. Recently, Kolner et al. [1] introduced a model, called Glimpse-based Active Perception (GAP), that selectively attends to salient areas of the image guided by selective visual attention mechanisms. Merging the spatial and visual information about the attended regions of interest (ROIs), GAP learns representations that generalize to out-of-distribution (OOD) visual content. Even though this approach demonstrates state-of-the-art OOD generalisation on several visual tasks, it has not been tested in real-world applications. This work extends the approach by incorporating bio-inspired, event-driven processing, enabling the model to efficiently handle dynamic visual inputs. Unlike traditional frame-based sensors that capture full images at fixed intervals, event-based cameras asynchronously detect changes in brightness with microsecond precision. This results in a highly efficient, low-latency stream of events with superior temporal resolution and reduced redundancy.

Methods The model depicted in Fig. 1 processes an input event frame to generate a saliency map from a saliency-based bioinspired visual attention model [2]. A winner-takes-all mechanism, combined with inhibition-of-return, is then applied to identify the next salient point in the visual field. These locations guide the glimpse sensor toward the most salient regions, which are marked by green circles and represent the localised glimpse contents. Both the glimpse ROIs and their corresponding coordinates are subsequently forwarded to the downstream architecture to associate sensorimotor contingencies.

Preliminary Results To obtain an early indication of the model’s ability to process event-based inputs, we evaluated it on a simple binary classification task from the SVRT dataset [3], in which the objective is to determine whether two shapes in an image are the same or different. The original static images were transformed into 4-second videos by introducing jittery motion, and subsequently converted into event streams using the ICNS Event Based Camera Simulator. The model received input in the form of event-frames (Fig.2). Preliminary results, shown in Tab.1, suggest that the model can effectively process event-based information, exhibiting only a minor decrease in performance compared to using standard pixel-based images.

Figure 1: Model architecture consisting of a glimpse sensor controlled by the saliency map to attend to different visual regions. The downstream architecture associates these regions with their spatial locations to make the final decision.

Figure 2: Input examples. The task is to determine whether two shapes are the same or different.

Input type		Classification accuracy
Pixel-based (original image)		0.99
Event-based	Moderate noise	0.93
	Strong noise	0.83

Table 1: Preliminary results: classification accuracy shows how often the model correctly determines whether two shapes are the same or different.

References

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